

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF FEMALE TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Qosimova Ozoda Xudoynazarovna

Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute, associate professor of the "Pedagogy" department

O'ktamboyeva Navbahor

Student of Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

Article information:

Manuscript received: 09 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Nov 2024; **Published:** 11 Dec 2024

Abstract: This article discusses the role and importance of female pedagogues in the education system. The article examines the place of female pedagogues in society, their role in ensuring gender equality in the education system, professional and personal development, influence on students and their contribution to social changes in society. The work of female teachers is of great importance not only in providing students with knowledge, but also in forming their moral and social values. Their professional activities and personal development play an important role in ensuring justice, equality and stability in society.

Keywords: women educators, education system, gender equality, professional development, social change, impact on students, personal development, sustainability in society, teacher's role, justice and equity.

The role and importance of women teachers in the education system affects all areas of society. Teachers, especially women, play an important role not only in imparting knowledge, but also in forming moral, cultural and social values in students. Their importance in the educational system is incomparable not only in academic achievements, but also in ensuring stability and equality in society.

Women teachers in the educational system of the society not only provide students with knowledge, but also affect their personality and future life. Female educators play a major role in teaching students not only academics, but also life experiences, values, and important social skills. They are a source of motivation for children and youth, inspiring teachers and active in bringing about social change. Female educators in particular have a special place in society: they are known for having relatively more emotion, patience and empathy in the field of education. These qualities help in working effectively as a teacher and in understanding students better.

Female pedagogues play an important role in ensuring gender equality in the education system. They help prevent gender stereotypes in society by teaching students basic values such as fairness, respect and equality. Active participation of women and girls in the education system helps to ensure that the most important thing in society is equal rights and opportunities for all citizens. Women teachers teach students how to behave, have self-respect and value others, which is an important step towards gender equality in society.

Professional growth and personal development of female teachers are necessary for the success of the educational system. They should constantly improve their skills, learn new methods and introduce innovations into the educational process. Participation in the professional development of female teachers increases their self-confidence, which in turn improves the quality of education. Women often struggle with family responsibilities to succeed in the teaching profession. However, they have achieved many

successes in maintaining a personal and professional balance. In this case, it is necessary to create support mechanisms from the state and society, to provide more opportunities to female teachers.

Female teachers not only provide students with scientific information, but also teach them life skills. Students learn many lessons from educators: values such as hard work, self-discipline, responsibility, and mutual respect. Female educators are often patient, kind, and attentive in their work and provide support to students. It helps not only academic but also personal development of students. The teacher's pedagogical approach, his interaction with students determines the quality of education.

Women teachers play an important role in the implementation of social changes in the society. By educating students based on justice, human rights, solidarity and other social values, they make society more stable and developed. Female pedagogues, especially, educate the future generation as socially responsible, mutually respectful and free-thinking individuals. It means their contribution in supporting and implementing change in society.

Women educators play several important roles in society that can bring about social change. Educators can actively participate not only in teaching, but also in shaping social and cultural values, ensuring gender equality and combating discrimination in society. Here are some directions:

1. **Gender Equality in Education:** Educators play a major role in promoting gender equality in society by encouraging and empowering women and girls in particular to pursue education. Social change can be achieved by emphasizing that there should be no barriers to education for girls.
2. **Capacity building:** Female educators can further increase their potential through education and find their place in social life. Helping women and girls to find their place in scientific, cultural and professional spheres, serves to increase their activity in society.
3. **Combating stereotypes:** Educators can combat stereotypes in society, particularly misconceptions about women and girls, through teaching. Showing women that they have more opportunities than just domestic work or a family role encourages social change.
4. **Changing family and social values:** Women teachers can teach their students and members of the community the correct understanding of their social role in the family and society and encourage them to live on the basis of equality, respect and justice.
5. **Training women for leadership:** Educators also play an important role in training women for leadership and management. Gender equality in society can be improved by helping women acquire the knowledge and skills they need to be educated and succeed in their fields.
6. **Calling the society for solidarity:** Women teachers, especially female teachers, can be active in the way of ensuring social justice and equality in the society. They can inform students and families about social issues and call for community involvement.

Thus, pedagogic women can greatly contribute to changes in society through their teaching, upbringing, and social activities. They play an important role not only in imparting knowledge, but also in fostering justice, equality, and respect in society.

In conclusion, the role and importance of female pedagogues in the education system is very great. They are of great importance not only in imparting knowledge to students, but also in forming their personality, values and attitude towards society. The role of female educators is important in ensuring gender equality in the education system, implementing social changes and supporting professional development. Therefore, their work and contribution is a necessary factor in bringing about development and changes in the society.

List of references

1. Toshpulatov, M. (2020). *Pedagogika va ta'lim tizimining rivojlanishida gender tenglik*. Toshkent: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Ta'lim vazirligi.
2. Karimova, N. (2019). *Pedagogik nazariya va amaliyot: Xotin-qizlarning ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni*. Tashkent: Ilm Ziyo.
3. Xusainov, A. (2021). *Pedagog xotin-qizlarning kasbiy o'sishiga oid muammolar va yechimlar*. O'zbekiston ta'limi, 1(5), 45-56.
4. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). INCREASING SOCIAL AND POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN OUR COUNTRY. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 249-255.
5. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). Technology Of Development Of Social Activity Of Female Pedagogues In The Conditions Of The New Renaissance. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(9), 4469-4471.
6. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). The Role of Innovative Technologies in the Quality Organization of the Educational Process of Female Teachers. *Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences*, 1(6), 133-136.
7. Касимова, О. Х. (2023). Роль Женщин И Девушек-Педагогов В Развитии Мышления Молодежи. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 389-392.
8. Касимова, О. Х. (2023). Повышение Социальной Активности Женщин-Учителей–Веление Времени. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 393-396.
9. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. Bobomurod o'g'li, BB, & Jaloliddin O'roz o'g, N.(2022). Increasing the Social Activity of Female Teachers is the Need of the Hour. *Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences*, 1(6), 137-139.
10. Qosimova, O., & Mamarasulov, U. (2022). THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGIC WOMEN AND GIRLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING OF YOUNG PEOPLE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 2392-2397.
11. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O., & Qurbonovich-Docent, U. U. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(6).
12. Bakhriddinovna, O. F. (2022). Methods of Studying Individual Characteristics and Abilities of Children. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 9, 58-61.
13. Sagdullayevich M. S., Bakhriddinovna O. F. Use of innovative pedagogical technologies based on modern rhythmic gymnastics for child. – 2022.
14. Norbo'tayev F. M., Imomova L. Z. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIO-PERSONAL KOMPETENT I IN SCHOOLCHILDREN-YOUTH //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 4. – C. 187-191.
15. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O., & Qurbonovich, U. U. (2022). A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN MOTIVATIONS FOR INCREASING THE QUALIFICATION OF TEACHER-WOMEN AND TEACHER-MALE. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(3).
16. Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich, X. L. A. qizi . (2023). THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN MEDICINE AND THE ISSUES OF ITS INFLUENCE ON HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY AND HEALTH. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(6), 297–300. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019314>
17. Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich, A. A. A. (2023). MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF MUSIC CLUBS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS.

INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(6), 94–97.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019320>

18. U.Utanov. (2023). THE USE OF ANCESTRAL HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURE & HORTICULTURE, 3(6), 95–100. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8055288>